

Reducing corruption in public procurement using machine learning

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Abstract

Public procurement processes are prone to corruption in many countries around the world. Many regulatory agencies that monitor and improve procurement use a manual and reactive review process. This makes it slow and expensive to detect and reduce corruption. In this work, we partnered with the National Agency for Public Procurement (DNCP) in Paraguay to take their current manual procurement review process and augment it with machine learning to complement the regulator’s work in automating reviews. Our system analyzes procurements when they are created and generates a risk score on whether procurement is likely to receive complaints (a proxy for corruption) in the future or not. Compared to a review on a first-come-first-served basis, we show that reviews based on our classification model improve the complaints capture rate from 30 percent to 78 percent. In addition, we consider equity, and balance efficiency with policy goals to reduce bias towards high value procurements in the review process. The result is a more efficient process, that is less bias towards high value procurements.

Keywords— classification; bias; corruption; procurement.

1 Introduction

Public procurement is the process in which governmental agencies and authorities purchase goods and services from companies with public funds. Effective public procurement functions enable the government to provide quality public goods and services that are beneficial to citizens and the growth of the economy [1]. Unfortunately, corrupt practices could chip away at this function and lead to severe conse-

quences¹ [2].

In Paraguay, the National Agency for Public Procurement (Dirección Nacional de Contrataciones Públicas, DNCP) is an independent regulator responsible for managing, monitoring and raising alerts on all public procurement processes that occur in Paraguay. DNCP receives on average 13,000 procurement applications each year and employs 30 reviewers to review these applications manually. Due to DNCP being resource-constrained and the review process being expensive, they can only thoroughly review a small number of those applications. Figure 1 below shows the public procurement process in summary.

Figure 1: **Existing public procurement process** - Public agencies publish their intention to procure items from the private sectors. These are reviewed by DNCP for any impediments to a fair and open bidding process. Potential bidders submit their bids and the winner gets the contract. If there is any malpractice, bidders can make a complaint and a judge decides if the procurement specifications need to be revised.

This paper presents an automatic detection system using machine learning to complement DNCP’s work to prevent corrupt practices through public procurement in Paraguay.

¹In Paraguay, a corruption scandal at the Ministry of Education and a collapsed school led to the resignation of the education minister Marta Lafuente in 2016, see: <https://www.abc.com.py/nacionales/estudiantes-paraguayos-tumbaron-a-lafuente-1476803.html>

The aim is to improve the detection of corrupt practices as early as possible so that tragedies are prevented and citizens can enjoy the quality public infrastructure and services that they deserve. While there were proof-of-concepts [3] drawn up for a similar purpose, this paper presents some of the key lessons learnt in building² and deploying a machine learning model for detecting public procurement corruption by a regulator on the ground.

2 Data used

DNCP has made its procurement data open and publicly available³. We partnered with DNCP and used 10 years of procurement data since 2011 containing 126,091 public procurement processes. Each process comes with sets of legal documents as well as metadata on the public agency involved, items procured, estimated cost of items, bidding companies, award outcome and whether there are any complaints received.

Since corruption is unobserved, we use complaints as a proxy (see Figure 1). Even if not all complaints are due to corruption, dealing with complaints is a resource-intensive process for DNCP. If we detect genuine complaints in advance, DNCP can allocate precious resources to investigate concerns at an earlier stage to prevent these from happening. Directly or indirectly, reducing genuine complaints will enable DNCP to combat corruption more effectively.

3 Methodology

From a data science perspective, the problem can be formulated as a classification problem. This means that the chosen algorithm aims to classify, on a daily basis, whether procurements received are likely to receive complaints in the future or not.

We generate quantitative features that are likely to correlate with complaints from both text documents⁴ as well as procurement metadata. Text features are keywords extracted from legal documents. We test various classification algorithms, such as logistic regressions, decision trees, random

forests, extra trees, XGBoost, LightGBM, SVM, and kNN, along with different combinations of hyperparameters.

During peak periods, our partners at DNCP estimated that they only have enough capacity and resources to scrutinise the top 30% of daily procurements received. Our evaluation metric is therefore recall @ 30% of the total daily procurements received, i.e. proportion of complaints captured by scrutinising 30% of all the daily procurements received based on our classifier’s probability ranking. This is compared with a baseline of reviewing 30% of daily procurements on a first-come-first-served basis. For model validation, we use a temporal-folding cross validation strategy illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: **Temporal-folding cross-validation.**

Training dataset for each fold is growing over time and the test set is one year ahead of data with a 90 days blind gap. This blind gap is designed to act as a buffer to ensure that there is no temporal leakage in our training set. The validation dataset is a holdout set of the latest one year of data.

In using machine learning algorithms for policy-making, we were aware of the potential biases that might propagate through our data. We conducted qualitative interviews with respective stakeholders (reviewers, judges, bidders and lawyers) to cross-check their experiences with the procurement process and our findings in the data and the model. We also anticipated that complaints data would not fully capture the extent of corruption and targeting complaints could potentially bias the model, resulting in a blind spot for the reviewers. We hence introduced equity metrics⁵ to penalise biased outcomes. This is elaborated upon in the next section.

²Github repo: <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/DSSG19-DNCP-PUBLIC>

³See: <https://www.contrataciones.gov.py/datos/data>

⁴Text features are keywords extracted from legal documents. We use a combination of Python text mining packages (PDFminer, pyPdf, and tika) to extract texts from PDFs. The main text features are based on term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) where less common words specific to a document occurring in high frequency are given higher weights.

⁵In order to implement equity metrics, we use the Aequitas package developed by the University of Chicago’s Center for Data Science and Public Policy. More specifically we used the equity parity metric that ensures all protected groups have equal representation in the selected set.

4 Results

Through interviews, we found that our classification model could be biased by behaviours of various actors. For example, we learnt from company lawyers that there are certain legal fees involved in making a complaint. This cost could potentially deter some small value procurements from being complained against. Hence, there is an overrepresentation of high-value procurements in the complaints data. In our model selection process, we penalise the models that place too much importance on the value of procurements in order to make the review process and outcomes more equitable.

Figure 3: **Comparison of recall curves optimised at 30% quality review.**

Figure 3 shows that ordering and scrutinising 3% of daily procurements by their monetary value would allow DNCP to capture 80% of all complaints, an effective heuristic. In fact, our best machine learning model, penalised for bias towards high valued procurements, performs slightly worse in terms of our recall metric at 78%.

Figure 4: **Distribution of procurements by value category.**

Figure 4 shows that our machine learning model forces the reviewers to review 30% more low value procurements than they would otherwise. This means that the machine learning model is more versatile and adaptable towards any

behavioural changes. If, as a result of automatic screening being publicised, more corrupted procurements are funnelled through low value procurements, the model is able to help reviewers prioritise those procurements better than the heuristic.

5 Deployment

DNCP has integrated the results of the machine learning model by introducing traffic-light indicators to reflect the risk levels of incoming procurements (red being the most risky) to the reviewers. The reviewers have received training so that they understand how the underlying indicators have been generated. Figure 5 and Figure 6 below shows the actual DNCP system interface.

Resultado de la Búsqueda
En esta sección podrá ver los resultados de la búsqueda realizada más arriba

Monto Total de los Llamados: 422.597.619.417

Id	Nombre	Mod.	Monto	Fecha Entrada	Entidad	Estado Público	Estado Interno	Derivado	Acción
373887	ADQUISICION DE PRODUCTOS ALIMENTICIOS PARA COMUNIDADES INDIGENAS - AD REFERENDUM 2020	CE	8.979.999.500	23/01/2020	Instituto Paraguayo del Indígena	No Publicado	Solicitar Verificación	Ulises Urutaga	[Icons]
370316	LLAMADO MOPC N° 2020/019 LICITACION PUBLICA NACIONAL PARA EL MEJORAMIENTO DE LA SEGURIDAD VIAL EN VARIOS TRAMOS DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS - AD REFERENDUM AL PRESUPUESTO GENERAL DE LA NACION 2020 ID 370316	LPN	183.240.049.822	24/01/2020	Ministerio de Obras Publicas y Comunicaciones	Publicado	Solicitar Verificación	Hugo Eduardo Fernandez	[Icons]
374056	CD N° 36-18 CONTRATACION DE SERVICIOS DE FISCALIZACION DE LA OBRA DE LA UNIDAD SANITARIA DE CAAZAPA - AD REFERENDUM 2020	CD	14.910.000	23/01/2020	Instituto de Prevision Social	No Publicado	Solicitar Verificación	Fanny Farías	[Icons]
374921	CONTRATACION DE FIRMA CERTIFICACION DEL SISTEMA DE GESTION DE LA CALIDAD NORMA ISO 9001:2015	CD	11.000.000	23/01/2020	Petroleos Paraguayos	No Publicado	Solicitar Verificación	Graciela Barreto	[Icons]
373682	CONSULTORIA EN GESTION DE PROYECTOS	LPN	16.923.400.000	24/01/2020	Empresa de Servicios Sanitarios del Paraguay	Publicado	Solicitar Verificación	Hugo Eduardo Fernandez	[Icons]
374591	C.D 05 "Adquisición de Insumos para departamento de Tránsito"	CD	29.912.500	23/01/2020	Municipalidad de San Ignacio	No Publicado	Solicitar Verificación	Jose Manuel Encina Guillen	[Icons]
374310	ADQUISICION DE CAJONES FUNEBRES	CD	700.000	23/01/2020	Gobierno Departamental de Paraguarí	No Publicado	Solicitar Verificación	Cristhian Benitez	[Icons]

Figure 5: **Overview of the system.** All procurements are listed to allow an easy search. Each process is already tagged with a traffic light (indicated by the red arrows) based on the model's output.

DNCP is now analysing the results of the model in production to move forward to the model re-training phase. This will allow DNCP to evaluate a possible reorganization of their internal processes and departments to improve the reviewing processes.

6 Conclusion

Corruption in the public procurement process is a complex problem to tackle. We demonstrate a first step in using machine learning techniques to help regulators in their work to efficiently identify likely problematic procurements. Further, by penalising models that are biased on a few key variables, we balance maximising our metric with a more equitable outcome that is more resilient to changing behaviours.

Modificación del Llamado
 A través de esta sección usted podrá cargar o modificar un llamado

Datos del Llamado: [Etapas y Plazos](#) | [Productos/Bienes/Servicios](#) | [Invitados/Documentos](#)

Riesgo de Protesta

Riesgo de protesta: ←

monto global estimado
 planificación: 2.227537072876024

tipo procedimiento: 0.983238921300354

categoria: -0.4493479933548748

Datos del Llamado

id: 370316 Nombre: LLAMADO MOPC N° 20220219 LICITACIÓN PÚBLICA NACIONAL PARA

* Descripción: LLAMADO MOPC N° 20220219 LICITACIÓN PÚBLICA NACIONAL PARA EL MEJORAMIENTO DE LA SEGURIDAD VIAL EN VARIOS TRAMOS DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS -AO RESERVADO AL PRESUPUESTO GENERAL DE LA NACIÓN Expediente: 332209

Preclasificación:

Monto Estimado: 183.240.040.822 Sistema de Adjudicación: A - Por Lote

Forma de pago: Carta Certificada Anticipo: 0.0 %

* Mantenimiento de Ofertas: 3.0 % * Vigencia del contrato: Hasta Duración Cumplimiento Total de Obligaciones Hasta Recepción Definitiva

Tipo de Redondeo Items: Hacia Abajo Estado: Solicitar Verificación

Proceso por Subasta: No

Figure 6: **Procurement profile.** Each individual process has a profile compiling the corresponding information, including the risk score resulting from the machine learning model.

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